

CENTRAL LUZON PUBLIC LIBRARIES: BUILDING INCLUSIVE SPACES THROUGH ANTIRACIST EDI KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the current state of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) knowledge and practices in public libraries of Central Luzon, Philippines. A survey was used to assess library staff's awareness and implementation of EDI initiatives. The findings will guide the development of a diversity management plan to promote inclusive library services. This research aims to address the gap in EDI research within Philippine librarianship.

Keywords: *public libraries, EDI (Equity, Diversity, Inclusion), anti-racism initiatives, diversity management plans, inclusive library services*

INTRODUCTION

Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) have become core principles for many institutions, moving beyond mere compliance obligations. Public libraries, as bastions of community engagement, have a responsibility to cultivate welcoming and inclusive spaces for all. This study explores the current state of EDI knowledge and practices within public libraries in Central Luzon, Philippines.

A recent report by the American Library Association (ALA) underlines the importance of EDI in libraries. The 2021 publication emphasizes the need for libraries to foster inclusive environments that reflect the diversity of their communities. This study builds upon this call to action by investigating the current landscape of EDI efforts in public libraries of Central Luzon.

By understanding the current state of EDI practices, this study seeks to empower libraries to create more inclusive spaces that serve all members of the community.

The Importance of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (EDI) in Libraries

Public libraries serve as cornerstones of a democratic society, providing free access to information and fostering a sense of community. The American Library Association (ALA) emphasizes this role in its Strategic Directions, highlighting libraries' essential role in enabling diverse communities to participate fully (ALA, 2017).

Diversity is not just a moral imperative; it strengthens libraries' ability to serve all patrons. Finch (2022) argues that exposure to diverse viewpoints and cultural experiences enhance critical thinking skills and cultural literacy. Libraries, as "nuclear social points" (Princh, 2021), have a unique opportunity to cultivate respect for individuals from different backgrounds through inclusive collections, programming, and services.

The Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) reinforces this notion in its Diversity Standards (2012), asserting that diversity is a core value for libraries and a societal necessity. A diverse and inclusive library environment empowers all patrons to reach their full potential (ACRL, 2012).

The Need for Strategic Diversity Management

The success of EDI efforts hinges on a well-defined strategic plan. The USAID Workplace Diversity Management Module (2018) outlines the importance of such a plan in establishing a clear rationale for investment and providing direction towards achieving diversity goals. The module details a comprehensive strategic planning process, encompassing needs assessments, goal setting, and strategy development (USAID, 2018).

Furthermore, the module outlines key steps for designing a diversity plan, including forming a task force, conducting a diversity audit, and establishing a strategic plan with measurable goals and objectives (USAID, 2018). Regular monitoring and evaluation are crucial for ensuring the plan's effectiveness (USAID, 2018).

Research Gap and Current Study's Contribution

While the importance of EDI in libraries is well-established, research on implementing and evaluating EDI initiatives in public libraries, particularly within the Philippine context, remains limited. Existing studies often focus on academic libraries or specific aspects of diversity, such as cultural competency or collection development (Luo & Agyei-Mensah, 2019; Koechler, 2018).

This study aims to address this gap by investigating the current state of EDI knowledge and practices in public libraries of Central Luzon, Philippines. By assessing the level of awareness, implementation, and potential gaps, this research will guide the development

of a practical diversity management plan specifically tailored to the needs of public libraries in the Philippines.

The proposed plan will contribute to the ongoing conversation on EDI in libraries by providing a framework for promoting inclusive services and fostering a welcoming environment for all patrons.

Synthesis

This literature review has established the critical role of EDI in libraries and the importance of strategic planning for successful implementation. However, research specifically focused on public libraries in the Philippines remains limited. This study aims to address this gap by investigating EDI knowledge and practices in Central Luzon public libraries. The findings will guide the development of a practical diversity management plan, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive library environment for all patrons within the Philippine context.

Research Questions

This study investigates Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) with a focus on antiracist practices in public libraries of Central Luzon, Philippines. It explores the current state of knowledge and implementation of these principles through three key research questions:

1. Knowledge of EDI Antiracism. How knowledgeable are public library personnel in Central Luzon about EDI principles, particularly regarding antiracism practices?
2. Implementation of EDI Antiracism. To what extent do public libraries in Central Luzon implement EDI and antiracism policies and procedures within administration, human resources, and service delivery?
3. Knowledge-Practice Gap. Is there a gap between the awareness of EDI antiracism principles and their actual implementation in Central Luzon public libraries?
4. Diversity Management Plan. How can a diversity management plan be designed to enhance EDI and antiracist practices in public libraries of Central Luzon?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to investigate the current state of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) knowledge and practices within public libraries of Central Luzon, Philippines. Descriptive research seeks to describe the characteristics of a population or phenomenon without manipulating variables or establishing cause-and-effect relationships (Tang & Chaw, 2016). This approach is well-suited for this study's

objectives, which aim to understand the level of awareness and implementation of EDI initiatives in public libraries.

The target population for this study consisted of all public libraries in Central Luzon that are affiliated with the National Library of the Philippines. A total of 22 libraries fell into this category. Participants were recruited through the Public Libraries Division. A written communication was sent to all 22 libraries inviting them to participate in an online survey.

Out of the 22 libraries contacted, 15 responded and completed the online survey, resulting in a response rate of 68.18%.

To assess EDI knowledge and implementation, the study employed a modified version of the EDI Antiracism Readiness Survey by Marci Ramiro-Jenkins. The modifications focused on grouping the survey items into three categories: administration, human resources, and service delivery. The survey form or research instrument has two parts. Part 1 obtained information on public libraries' level of knowledge on EDI Antiracism policies and practices. Data on the degree of EDI Antiracism policies and practices implementation were acquired in Part 2.

The modified questionnaire was validated using face validation where two experts (e.g., reference librarian in a public library, and a library educator-researcher) had been invited to check the applicability of the items and the categories under which the items were clustered.

After the questionnaire was test piloted, the Cronbach alpha was computed using JAMOVI to check the internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire. The computed Cronbach alpha is 0.822 which is good.

Descriptive statistics, including frequency distribution, percentiles, ranking, mean, and standard deviation, were employed to analyze the collected data. These methods helped to present, summarize, and interpret the findings related to the level of knowledge and implementation of EDI/antiracism policies and practices within the public libraries.

Range Interval	Descriptive Rating/Interpretation
4.17 – 5.00	Completely Extensive
3.35 – 4.18	Highly Extensive
2.51 – 3.34	Moderate
1.67 – 2.50	Somewhat Limited
0.83 – 1.66	Very Limited
0.00 – 0.82	No Provision at All

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the EDI Antiracism level of knowledge of public libraries in terms of administration. Among the indicators, public libraries have highly extensive level of knowledge on implementing antiracism policies (mean=3.93; SD=2.58), acting on biased, racist, and xenophobic behaviour from staff and patrons, and reframing from generalization (mean=3.86; SD=0.833, SD=0.743, respectively). Meanwhile, public libraries' level of knowledge on the implementation of internal policies for responding to hate speech, hate crimes, and hate propaganda at the library is moderate (mean=3.26; SD=0.457). Generally, it was reported that public libraries' level of knowledge is highly extensive in terms of administration (mean=3.82; SD=0.489).

Table 1.

EDI Antiracism Knowledge Level of Public Libraries in Terms of Administration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Implementing of library antiracist policies	3.93	0.258	Highly Extensive
2. Advocating library commitment to diversity, equity, inclusion, and antiracism	4.26	0.457	Completely Extensive
3. Implementing internal policies for responding to hate speech, hate crimes, and hate propaganda at the library	3.26	0.457	Moderate
4. Acting on biased, racist, and xenophobic behaviour from staff and patrons	3.86	0.743	Highly Extensive
5. Reframing from generalization	3.86	0.833	Highly Extensive
6. Including persons with disabilities in the planning, implementing, and evaluating of library services, programs, and facilities	3.80	0.676	Highly Extensive
Total	3.82	0.489	Highly Extensive

Table 2 presents the EDI antiracism knowledge level of public libraries in terms of human resources. In general, public libraries' level of knowledge in terms of human resources is highly extensive (mean=3.79; SD=0.763) similar with their knowledge level in terms of administration. Supporting equal employment opportunity for gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender and other LGBTQ+ librarians and library workers (mean=3.93; SD=0.798), increasing diversity through job postings and hiring practices (mean=3.60; SD=1.242), and supporting staff from underrepresented groups (mean=3.53; SD=0.833) are among the indicators which at the top of the list in terms of their knowledge level on human resources.

Among the other indicators, developing pathway on reporting microaggressions, emotional labour, or sharing experiences that reflect racial inequity, disadvantages, or oppression was reported to be moderate (mean=3.26; SD=0.457), while supporting for

continuing professional development, professional growth, and success was the indicator which is on the top of the list (mean=4.66; SD=0.487).

Table 2.

EDI Antiracism Knowledge Level of Public Libraries in Terms of Human Resources

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Increasing diversity through job postings and hiring practices	3.60	1.242	Highly Extensive
2. Supporting staff from underrepresented groups	3.53	0.833	Highly Extensive
3. Supporting equal employment opportunity for gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender and other LGBTQ+ librarians and library workers	3.93	0.798	Highly Extensive
4. Supporting for continuing professional development, professional growth, and success	4.66	0.487	Completely Extensive
5. Developing pathway on reporting microaggressions, emotional labour, or sharing experiences that reflect racial inequity, disadvantages, or oppression	3.26	0.457	Moderate
Total	3.79	0.763	Highly Extensive

Table 3 presents the EDI antiracism knowledge level of public libraries in terms of services. Public libraries' level of knowledge on discouraging racial discrimination of a patron or a co-worker is completely extensive (mean=4.33; SD=0.487), while their knowledge on conducting equity evaluations to determine the unfairly impact or service among members of their community is moderate (mean=2.73; SD=0.928).

Table 3.

EDI Antiracism Knowledge Level of Public Libraries in Terms of Services

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Providing bilingual or multilingual staff at the library to serve its demographic needs	1.93	0.798	Somewhat Limited
2. Providing library facilities that serve patrons with disabilities	2.33	0.975	Somewhat Limited
3. Integrating of assistive technology to meet the needs of people with a broad range of disabilities (including learning, mobility, sensory, and developmental disabilities)	2.26	1.032	Somewhat Limited
4. Discouraging racial discrimination of a patron or a co-worker	4.33	0.487	Completely Extensive

5. Conducting equity evaluations to determine unfairly impact or service among members of their community	2.73	0.928	Moderate
6. Removing of communication barriers (by providing translation services in other languages according to demographic needs)	1.06	0.771	Very Limited
Total	2.92	0.998	Moderate

Table 4 presents the implementation level on EDI antiracism policies and practices in public libraries in terms of administration. In general, the implementation level of antiracism policies and practices is moderate (mean = 2.92; SD = 0.888), particularly on advocating library commitment to diversity, equity, inclusion, and antiracism (mean = 3.20; SD = 0.909), implementing of library antiracist policies (mean = 3.06; SD = 0.771), and acting on biased, racist, and xenophobic behaviour from staff and patrons (mean = 2.80; SD = 1.107). While public libraries have highly extensive level of implementation on reframing from generalization (mean = 3.93; SD = 0.771), they have somewhat limited level of implementation on implementing internal policies for responding to hate speech, hate crimes, and hate propaganda at the library (mean = 2.53; SD = 0.956), and in including persons with disabilities in the planning, implementing, and evaluating library services, programs, and facilities (mean = 2.00; SD = 0.816).

Table 4.
Level of Implementation of EDI Antiracism in Terms of Administration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Implementing of library antiracist policies	3.06	0.771	Moderate
2. Advocating library commitment to diversity, equity, inclusion, and antiracism	3.20	0.909	Moderate
3. Implementing internal policies for responding to hate speech, hate crimes, and hate propaganda at the library	2.53	0.956	Somewhat limited
4. Acting on biased, racist, and xenophobic behaviour from staff and patrons	2.80	1.107	Moderate
5. Reframing from generalization	3.93	0.771	Highly Extensive
6. Including persons with disabilities in the planning, implementing, and evaluating of library services, programs, and facilities	2.00	0.816	Somewhat Limited
Total	2.92	0.888	Moderate

Table 5 presents the extent of implementation of EDI antiracism policies and practices in public libraries in terms of human resources. In general, the implementation level of antiracism in terms of human resources is moderate (mean = 2.91; SD = 0.749), particularly in supporting staff from underrepresented groups (mean = 3.06; SD = 0.853), increasing diversity through job postings and hiring practices (mean = 2.67; SD = 0.942), and in supporting equal opportunity for gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender and other LGBTQ+ librarians and library workers (mean = 2.60; SD = .0711). It was reported that public libraries have highly extensive level of implementation on supporting for continuing professional development, professional growth, and success (mean = 3.93; SD = 0.771), while their implementation level on developing pathway on reporting microaggressions, emotional labour, or sharing experiences that reflect racial inequity, disadvantages, or oppression is somewhat limited (mean = 2.33; SD = 0.471).

Table 5.
Level of Implementation of EDI Antiracism in Terms of Human Resources

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Increasing diversity through job postings and hiring practices	2.67	0.942	Moderate
2. Supporting staff from underrepresented groups	3.06	0.853	Moderate
3. Supporting equal employment opportunity for gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender and other LGBTQ+ librarians and library workers	2.60	0.711	Moderate
4. Supporting for continuing professional development, professional growth, and success	3.93	0.771	Highly Extensive
5. Developing pathway on reporting microaggressions, emotional labour, or sharing experiences that reflect racial inequity, disadvantages, or oppression	2.33	0.471	Somewhat Limited
Total	2.91	0.749	Moderate

Table 6 presents the level of implementation of EDI antiracism policies and practices in public libraries in terms of services. Public libraries have very limited level of implementation on removing of communication barriers (by providing translation services in other languages according to demographic needs) (mean = 1.73; SD = 0.679), providing library facilities that serve patrons with disabilities (mean = 1.53; SD = 0.805), providing bilingual or multilingual staff at the library to serve its demographic needs (mean = 1.40; SD = 0.711), and in integrating of assistive technology to meet the needs of people with a broad range of disabilities (including learning, mobility, sensory, and developmental disabilities) (mean = 1.33; SD = 0.699). While public libraries' level of implementation on discouraging racial discrimination of a patron or a co-worker is highly extensive (mean =

3.67; SD = SD = 0.942), conducting equity evaluations to determine the unfairly impact or service among members of their community is found to be moderate (mean = 2.80; SD = 0.832).

Table 6.
Level of Implementation of EDI Antiracism in Terms of Services

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Providing bilingual or multilingual staff at the library to serve its demographic needs	1.40	0.711	Very Limited
2. Providing library facilities that serve patrons with disabilities	1.53	0.805	Very Limited
3. Integrating of assistive technology to meet the needs of people with a broad range of disabilities (including learning, mobility, sensory, and developmental disabilities)	1.33	0.699	Very Limited
4. Discouraging racial discrimination of a patron or a co-worker	3.67	0.942	Highly Extensive
5. Conducting equity evaluations to determine unfairly impact or service among members of their community	2.80	0.832	Moderate
6. Removing of communication barriers (by providing translation services in other languages according to demographic needs)	1.73	0.679	Very Limited
Total	2.07	0.778	Somewhat Limited

To determine whether there are any significant differences between the level of awareness and application of EDI policies and practices in public libraries, an independent T-test was used. The average scores for level knowledge and implementation were 3.83 (SD = 0.18), as shown in Table 7, and 2.92 (SD = 0.77), respectively. The outcome demonstrates that there is a statistically significant difference between public libraries' awareness and implementation of EDI policies and practices [$t(15) = 3.61687, p > .05$]. Compared to their level of implementation, public libraries' knowledge in this context indicated a greater level.

Table 7.

Mean Scores and T-Values Difference in Level of Knowledge Implementation of EDI Policies and Practices in Terms of Administration

Level of Extent (Administration)	n	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig.
Knowledge	15	3.83	0.18	28	3.61687	.001162
Implementation	15	2.92	0.77			

Significant at P < .05 (2-tailed)

The mean scores on level knowledge and implementation of EDI policies and practices in public libraries, as shown in Table 8, were 3.80 (SD = 0.23) and 2.92 (SD = 0.34), respectively, in terms of human resources. There was a substantial disparity between knowledge level and implementation [t (15) = 4.49073, p > .05]. In other words, in terms of human resources, the level of expertise of public libraries does not match the level of their application of EDI policies and practices.

Table 8.

Mean Scores and T-Values Difference in Level of Knowledge and Implementation of EDI Policies and Practices in Terms of Human Resources

Level of Extent (Human Resources)	n	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig.
Knowledge	15	3.80	0.23	28	4.49073	.000111
Implementation	15	2.92	0.34			

Significant at P < .05 (2-tailed)

Another independent T-test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference in terms of services between the level of knowledge and implementation of EDI policies and practices in public libraries. Table 9 shows that the mean levels of knowledge and implementation were 2.44 (SD = 0.10) and 2.08 (SD = 0.13), respectively. The findings indicate that there is a statistically significant difference [t (15) = 2.94656, p > .05] between public library knowledge and implementation of EDI policies and practices. In this context, public libraries' knowledge demonstrated a higher level than their implementation level.

Table 9.

Mean Scores and T-Values Difference in Level of Knowledge and Implementation of EDI Policies and Practices in Terms of Services

Level of Extent (Services)	n	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig.
Knowledge	15	2.44	0.10	28	2.94656	.006409
Implementation	15	2.08	0.13			

Significant at P < .05 (2-tailed)

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the application of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) principles in public libraries of Central Luzon, Philippines. The findings reveal a significant discrepancy between public libraries' awareness of EDI concepts and their actual implementation (Tables 7, 8, & 9). Across all three categories (administration, human resources, and services), libraries exhibited a statistically higher level of knowledge compared to implementation.

This aligns with existing research in library and information science (LIS). Finch (2022) emphasizes the potential of libraries as institutions that can promote social justice by challenging the status quo. However, several studies point to challenges in translating EDI values into actionable practices. Koechler (2018) highlights the need for concrete strategies and ongoing evaluation for effective EDI implementation in academic libraries. Similarly, Luo & Agyei-Mensah (2019) call for practical frameworks to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application of diversity initiatives within academic libraries.

The current study suggests several factors potentially contributing to this knowledge-practice gap in public libraries:

- Limited Resources. Inadequate staff time and funding for training and development programs can hinder effective EDI implementation (ACRL, 2012).
- Unclear Goals. The lack of clear and measurable goals for EDI initiatives makes it difficult to track progress and hold libraries accountable (USAID, 2018).
- Resistance to Change. Potential resistance from library staff or the communities served might create roadblocks to implementing inclusive practices.

Conclusions

In terms of administration and human resources, public libraries have extensive knowledge of EDI antiracism policies and practices, while services are moderate. Meanwhile, the level of implementation of EDI antiracism policies and practices is moderate in terms of administration and human resources, and services are somewhat limited.

It was discovered that there was a statistically significant difference between public libraries' awareness and implementation of EDI policies and practices in terms of administration. In comparison to their level of implementation, public libraries' knowledge in this context was higher. In terms of human resources, public libraries' level of expertise does not correspond to the extent to which they apply EDI policies and practices. In terms

of services, public libraries' knowledge demonstrated a higher level of implementation than their knowledge level.

Recommendations

While Marci Ramiro-Jenkins's EDI Antiracism Readiness Survey provides a foundation for determining whether a specific public library is ready to implement antiracism policies and practices, it is recommended that public libraries continuously assess their level of readiness. The proposed Diversity Management Plan for public libraries is recommended during the process.

(Public Library) Diversity Management Plan

Plan period: from – to

Message from the Public Library Head

Definitions

Diversity: representing and integrating people with diverse characteristics and backgrounds into our organization.

Inclusion: valuing and respecting the uniqueness of our people and providing them with the opportunity and support needed for them to contribute to organizational mission and goals.

Focus Areas

- Equitable Administration
- Diversified Human Resources
- Inclusive Services

Focus Area	Diversified Human Resources
Goal	Create an empowering and inclusive work environment and culture in which employees can fully contribute their abilities.
Objective 1	Encourage a healthy balance of work and personal life.
Strategy 1.1	Implement flexible work arrangements
Activities	1.1.1 Create policies and procedures to support flexible work arrangements. 1.1.2 Inform all employees of new policies and procedures via email and during staff meetings.
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Created and distributed flexible policies and procedures to all employees • The number of employees who benefit from flexible working arrangements.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work-life balance issues reduced turnover rate by (percent)
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Objective 2	Support staff for continuing professional development, professional growth, and success
Strategy 2.1	Help employees with their professional development, growth, and success.
Activities	2.1.1 Create a workplace diversity and inclusion training manual 2.1.2 Create a training plan 2.1.3 Organize training sessions 2.1.4 Create a report on training workshops that have been implemented, including training evaluation.
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees participated in diversity and inclusion training (percent) • Employees said the training improved their understanding of workplace diversity and inclusion concepts (percent)

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical research principles by ensuring informed consent from all participants. Participants were informed that their participation was voluntary and would not incur any cost.

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